

Isosurface Maps Accompanying the Dataset “Hydrographic and Sediment Geochemical Data of the Northeastern Taiwan Strait”

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Figure 1. Water-column conditions during the cruise NOR3-0104 in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Water depth, (b) surface-water salinity (S_{sw}), (c) bottom-water temperature (T_{bw}), (d) bottom-water dissolved oxygen (DO_{bw}), (e) bottom-water total suspended matter (TSM_{bw}), and (c) full depth-integrated chlorophyll a content ($\text{Chl } a_{int}$). White dots denote the sampling sites. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b of this document) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 2. Sedimentological properties in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Water content, (b) mean grain size (M_z), and (c) ^{210}Pb -based mass accumulation rate (MAR). The black and white dots are marine sediment sampling sites from previous (Huh et al., 2011; Liao et al., 2018; Tao et al., 2023) and present studies, respectively. Data of the riverine TSM (stars) and sediment (squares; Lin et al., 2020) are also displayed, with colors corresponding to the color key. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 3. Bulk geochemical properties of sediment in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Organic carbon (OC) content, (b) atomic C/N ratio, (c) stable carbon isotopic ratio of OC ($\delta^{13}C_{OC}$), (d) ^{14}C -based fraction modern (Fm) of OC, and (e) fraction modern of terrestrial biosphere organic matter (Fm_{terr}) resolved from a three-endmember mixing model. The black and white dots are marine sediment sampling sites from previous (Liao et al., 2018; Tao et al., 2023) and present studies, respectively. Data of the riverine TSM (triangles = Hilton et al., 2010; Kao et al., 2014; stars = this study) and sediment (squares; Lin et al., 2020) are also displayed, with colors corresponding to the color key. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 4. Outputs of the three-endmember mixing model. (a to c) Fraction of terrestrial biosphere, marine, and petrogenic OC (f_{terr} , f_{mar} , and f_{petro}). (d to f) Content of OC of terrestrial biosphere, marine, and petrogenic origin (OC_{terr} , OC_{mar} , and OC_{petro}). (g to i) Flux of OC of terrestrial biosphere, marine, and petrogenic origin (F_{terr} , F_{mar} , and F_{petro}). White dots denote the sampling sites. Data of the riverine TSM (triangles; Kao et al., 2014) and sediment (squares; Lin et al., 2020) are also displayed, with colors corresponding to the color key. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 5. Organic geochemical properties of sediment in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Content of eight lignin monomers ($\Sigma 8$), (b) OC-normalized content of eight lignin monomers ($\Lambda 8$), (c) mass ratio of vanillin to vanillic acid ($(Al/Ad)_v$), (d) content of total hydrolyzable amino acids (THAA), (e) OC-normalized content of THAA (THAA'), and (f) THAA-based degradation index (DI). White dots denote the sampling sites. Data of the riverine TSM (stars) are also displayed, with colors corresponding to the color key. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 6. Organic geochemical properties of sediment in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Content of Chl a, (b) OC-normalized content of Chl a (Chl a'), (c) content of pheopigments a (Pheo a), (d) OC-normalized content of Pheo a (Pheo a'), and (e) mass ratio of Chl a to Pheo a (Chl a/Pheo a). White dots denote the sampling sites. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 7. Organic geochemical properties of sediment in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Content of cholesterol (CHOE), (b) OC-normalized content of cholesterol (CHOE'), (c) content of coprostanol (COP), (d) OC-normalized content of coprostanol (COP'), and (e) mass ratio of COP to the sum of COP and cholesterol (COP/(COP+CHOA)). White dots denote the sampling sites. Data of the riverine TSM (stars) are also displayed, with colors corresponding to the color key. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

Figure 8. Sedimentary oxygen consumption rates in the northeastern Taiwan Strait. (a) Total oxygen uptake normalized to 25 °C (TOU₂₅), (b) dissolved oxygen uptake normalized to 25 °C (DOU₂₅), and (c) benthos-mediated oxygen uptake at 25 °C (BMU₂₅). White dots denote the sampling sites. The thick gray line denotes the boundary ($\Phi = 5$; Fig. 2b) of the mud belt core area.

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